

Synthesis of Some Di- β -lactam and Di-thiazolidinone Ring Systems

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Symmetric and asymmetric 1,4-diarylidene phenylenediamines were reacted with chloroacetyl chloride or mercaptoacetic acid to afford di- β -lactam or di-thiazolidin-4-one ring systems. A model containing both the β -lactam and thiazolidin-4-one moieties was prepared.

β -LACTAMS received a great interest after the discovery that penicillin and cephalosporin possess this heterocyclic system¹. The observed chemotherapeutic efficiency of thiazolidin-4-one²⁻⁷ is of interest and justifies a detailed study of the toxicological properties of the most active compounds. Keeping this in mind we report the studies on these two systems. The synthesis of the compounds was achieved in two steps, viz. (i) preparation of the key intermediates, symmetric and asymmetric 1,4-diarylidene phenylenediamine (**1a-h**) and (ii) cycloaddition of the key intermediates on chloroacetyl chloride or mercaptoacetic acid.

The reaction of *p*-phenylenediamine (1 mole) with aromatic aldehydes (2 mole) in boiling ethanol using piperidine as a catalyst afforded the symmetric 1,4-diarylidene derivatives (**1a-e**). The asymmetric ones were prepared by reacting a monoarylidene phenylenediamine with the appropriate aldehyde. The monoarylidene *p*-phenylenediamine derivatives were obtained by mixing the aromatic aldehydes with *p*-phenylenediamine (2 : 3 ratio) in absolute ethanol containing a catalytic amount of piperidine. The mixture was left at room temp. for 24 hr when the desired products were obtained. The structure of the symmetric (**1a-e**) and asymmetric (**1f-h**) derivatives was confirmed by elemental analyses and ir spectra.

The cycloaddition reaction of chloroacetyl chloride on the key intermediates (**1a-h**) was carried out in dry benzene or dry dioxane using triethylamine as an acid binding agent, to give the corresponding di- β -lactam systems (**2a-h**). The structure of all the products was confirmed by elemental analyses and ir spectra which showed characteristic absorption peaks at 1750-1730 cm^{-1} and between 780-750 cm^{-1} attributed to C=O (monocyclic β -lactam) and C-Cl, respectively.

The cycloaddition of mercaptoacetic acid on **1a-h** is possible and results in thiazolidinone formation^{8,9}. The reaction was performed by stirring a mixture of the key intermediates with mercaptoacetic acid in dry benzene or dry dioxane followed

- 1,2,3 a : Ar = Ar' = C₆H₅
 b : Ar = Ar' = *p*-NO₂C₆H₄
 c : Ar = Ar' = *p*-ClC₆H₄
 d : Ar = Ar' = *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄
 e : Ar = Ar' = α -C₁₀H₇
 f : Ar = C₆H₅ ; Ar' = *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄
 g : Ar = *p*-NO₂C₆H₄ ; Ar' = *p*-OCH₃C₆H₄
 h : Ar = *p*-NO₂C₆H₄ ; Ar' = *p*-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄

by refluxing the reaction mixture to ensure completion. The structure of the prepared dithiazolidin-4-ones (**3a-h**) was established by elemental analysis and spectral data. The ir spectra show absorption bands in the 1725-1690 cm^{-1} region due to C=O.

Aiming to obtain a model containing both the β -lactam and the thiazolidin-4-one systems we started with compound **2d** and subjected it to a two steps procedure with chloroacetyl chloride and mercaptoacetic acid and were able to isolate compounds **4** and **5**, respectively.

Experimental

All melting points reported are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Pye Unicam SP 200G spectrophotometer using KBr discs.

TABLE 1—1,4-DI(3-CHLORO-4-ARYL-2-AZETIDINON-1-YL)BENZENES (2a-h)

Comp.	Ar	Ar'	m.p. °C	Molecular formula (Mol. Wt.)	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1a	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	149	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ (284)	84.61 (84.50)	5.70 (5.63)	9.80 (9.85)
1b	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	252	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ (374)	64.31 (64.17)	3.67 (3.74)	14.70 (14.97)
1c	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	214	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₂ (353)	67.80 (67.98)	3.99 (3.96)	8.07 (7.93)
1d	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	210	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ (344)	76.82 (76.74)	5.99 (5.81)	8.19 (8.13)
1e	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	184	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ (384)	87.44 (87.50)	5.29 (5.20)	7.40 (7.29)
1f	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	180	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ ON ₂ (314)	80.19 (80.25)	5.91 (5.73)	9.00 (8.91)
1g	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	178	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ (359)	70.34 (70.19)	4.54 (4.73)	11.80 (11.69)
1h	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	250	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ (358)	73.54 (73.74)	5.67 (5.58)	11.65 (11.73)

TABLE 2—1,4-DI(2-ARYL-4-THIAZOLIDIN-4-ONE-3-YL)BENZENES (3a-h)

Comp.	Ar	Ar'	m.p. °C	Molecular formula (Mol. Wt.)	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
3a	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	255	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ (492)	66.47 (66.66)	4.54 (4.62)	6.60 (6.48)
3b	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	286	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ (522)	55.23 (55.17)	3.36 (3.44)	10.84 (10.72)
3c	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	203	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ S ₂ (501)	57.43 (57.48)	3.48 (3.59)	5.64 (5.58)
3d	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	225	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ (492)	63.54 (63.41)	4.77 (4.87)	5.75 (5.69)
3e	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	179	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ (532)	72.29 (72.18)	4.36 (4.51)	5.31 (5.26)
3f	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	198	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ (462)	64.88 (64.93)	4.84 (4.76)	6.14 (6.06)
3g	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	241	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ (475)	63.22 (63.15)	4.58 (4.42)	8.91 (8.84)
3h	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	190	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂ (520)	60.09 (60.00)	4.71 (4.61)	10.00 (10.76)

TABLE 3—1-(2-*p*-METHOXYPHENYL-THIAZOLIDIN-4-ONE-3-YL)-4-(4-*p*-METHOXYPHENYL-AZETIDIN-2-ONE-1-YL)BENZENES (5)

Comp.	Ar	Ar'	m.p. °C	Molecular formula (Mol. Wt.)	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
4	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	210	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄ Cl (420.5)	68.60 (68.48)	5.09 (4.99)	6.52 (6.65)
5	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	267	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄ ClS (494.5)	63.17 (63.09)	4.58 (4.65)	5.77 (5.66)

1,4-Di(3-chloro-4-aryl-2-azetidinon-1-yl)benzene (2a-h) : To a well stirred solution of symmetric or asymmetric diarylidene anils (1a-h) (0.1 mole) and triethylamine (0.1 mole) in dry benzene, an equimolecular amount of chloroacetyl chloride was added dropwise at room temp. The mixture was then stirred for 8 hr and left standing for 3 days. The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off and washed thoroughly with dry benzene. The combined filtrate was washed with dil. HCl, then with water and dried over magnesium sulphate.

After filtration the solvent was evaporated *in vacuo* and the residue which solidifies with ether was crystallized from the proper solvent. The results are listed in Table 1.

1,4-Di(2-aryl-4-thiazolidin-4-one-3-yl)benzene (3a-h) : Mercaptoacetic acid (0.15 mole) was added to a well stirred solution of symmetric or asymmetric diarylidene anils (1a-h) (0.1 mole) in dry benzene (70 ml) or dry dioxane. The mixture was stirred for 6 hr and then refluxed for 4 hr. The precipitated

product was filtered off and crystallized from the proper solvent. The results are listed in Table 2.

1-(2-p-Methoxyphenyl-thiazolidin-4-one-3-yl)-4-(4-p-methoxyphenyl-azetid-2-one-1-yl)benzene (5): This was prepared starting with **2d** (0.1 mole), triethylamine (0.1 mole) in dry benzene (100 ml). The mixture was stirred and an equimolecular amount of chloroacetyl chloride was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was stirred for 8 hr and then worked up as before to obtain after crystallization the 4-*p*-methoxyphenyl-1-(*p*-methoxybenzylidene aminophenyl)-azetid-2-one (**4**). The ir spectrum of this product showed an absorption peak at 1743 cm^{-1} (monocyclic β -lactam) and a band at 765 cm^{-1} for C-Cl bond. **4** was reacted with mercaptoacetic acid according to procedure mentioned earlier when we were able to isolate the

title product (**5**). The ir spectrum of this product indicates the presence of an additional C=O absorption of thiazolidinone ring at 1700 cm^{-1} . The analytical results are listed in Table 3.

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